

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on climate change data for historical and future scenarios at fine spatial resolution and indicators for sectoral analysis

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

DELIVERABLE D8.3

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework - NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D8.3 is based on the analysis of climate conditions for actual and future periods under two different climate scenarios and indicators for conducting specific analysis for climate change impacts on vineyards or other cultivations. Climate specific indicators are produced at a fine spatial scale (2,2 km), both for current climate period and future scenarios.

Introduction

CMCC is collaborating on the Flagship Project VINO part of NODES Spoke 6 by providing bioclimatic information for impact analyses on vineyards or other cultivations characterized by high spatial and temporal resolution. Bioclimatic indicators are derived using atmospheric variables based on dynamic downscaling climate simulations produced by CMCC.

Generally, the General Circulation Models (GCMs) with a low spatial resolution are mainly used for developing climate change scenarios and for large scale studies (Giorgi et al. 1990). GCMs cannot be used to represent climate variability at local scale and to obtain information for localized areas motivated by the requirement of policymakers for detailed regional scenarios of climate change. Therefore, it is important to downscale from larger scale models to a much finer scale in order to investigate climate variability at a more appropriate resolution and local scale. Dynamical downscaling method involves regionalizing GCM output to specific areas by combining the primitive equations associated with continuity, momentum and thermodynamic processes with surface characteristics of the region of interest, such as terrain, land cover and land-use and others. A number of different regional models (RCMs) have been widely used to dynamically downscale from the synoptic and larger scale atmospheric circulation in order to provide climate high-resolution information. Nowadays RCM also run simulations at very high spatial and temporal resolution (1-3km horizontal resolution and hourly frequency output). Climate data based on simulations run with single model are available at CMCC over the Italian peninsula at high spatial and temporal resolution (2.2km and sub-daily frequencies). The usage of climate information from a single climate model is not recommended in downstream applications (e.g., to support decision-making and adaptation) due to the unavailability of an evaluation of uncertainty associated to the model.

CMCC run long-term climate simulations over the Italian peninsula at 2.2km of resolution forced by ERA5 Reanalyses for evaluation experiment (VHR-REA_IT) and driven by CMIP5 GCM under IPCC RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios (VHR-PRO_IT). The outputs of the climate simulations are available on CMCC Data Delivery System (<https://dds.cmcc.it/>) in NetCDF format with reference coordinate system is WGS84 (EPSG 4326). Climate data coming from these simulations were largely used

(since 2016) in several studies demonstrating the good performances of its results (Prein et al. 2015).

Evaluation experiment (driven by ERA5): VHR-REA_IT

The data produced by dynamical downscaling of ERA5 (Hersbach et al. 2020) reanalysis (VHR-REA_IT, Raffa et al. 2021, Adinolfi et al. 2023) are at convection permitting scale (horizontal grid spacing 0.02° , 2.2 km) over the domain covering the Italian Peninsula (Lon = 5° W– 20° E; Lat = 36° N– 48° N) for the period from 1989 to 2020.

The dynamical downscaling activity is performed with the regional climate model COSMO model (Rockel et al. 2008) in CLimate Mode (COSMO-CLM) through a direct simulation (i.e., without nesting runs). In Figure 1, the domain covered by the simulation and the adopted strategy are reported. The output variables have an hourly frequency and are listed in Table 1.

Figure 1: Domain of ERA5 dynamical downscaling over Italy

Long Name	Short Name	Units	Description
2 m temperature	T_2M	K	Temperature of air at 2 m above surface
2 m dew point temperature	TD_2M	K	Temperature to which the air, at 2 m above surface, would have to be cooled for saturation to occur
Total precipitation	TOT_PREC	kg m ⁻²	Accumulated liquid and frozen water, comprising rain and snow, that falls to the surface
U-component of 10 m wind	U_10M	m s ⁻¹	Eastward component of the 10 m wind
V-component of 10 m wind	V_10M	m s ⁻¹	Northward component of the 10 m wind
2 m maximum temperature	TMAX_2M	K	Maximum temperature of air at 2 m above surface
2 m minimum temperature	TMIN_2M	K	Minimum temperature of air at 2 m above surface
mean sea level pressure	PMSL	Pa	The pressure (force per unit area) of the atmosphere at the surface
specific humidity	QV_2M	kg kg ⁻¹	The mass fraction of water vapor in (moist) air
total cloud cover	CLCT	1	Proportion of a grid box covered by cloud; cloud fractions vary from 0 to 1
Surface Evaporation	AEVAP_S	kg m ⁻²	Accumulated amount of water that has evaporated from the surface
Averaged surface net downward shortwave radiation	ASOB_S	W m ⁻²	Amount of solar radiation (also known as shortwave radiation) that reaches a horizontal plane at the surface (both direct and diffuse) minus the amount reflected by the surface (which is governed by the albedo)
Averaged surface net downward longwave radiation	ATHB_S	W m ⁻²	Thermal radiation (also known as longwave or terrestrial radiation) refers to radiation emitted by the atmosphere, clouds and the surface. This parameter is the difference between downward and upward thermal radiation at the surface
Surface snow amount	W_SNOW	m	Liquid water equivalent thickness of surface snow amount
Soil (multi levels) water content	W_SO	m	Liquid water equivalent thickness of moisture content of soil layer

Table 1: List of available variables

Climate projections: VHR-PRO_IT

Climate projections (VHR-PRO_IT, Raffa et al. 2023) are obtained at convection permitting scale (≈ 2.2 km resolution) by dynamically downscaling CMCC-CM global model (Scoccimarro et al. 2011) over the period 1989-2070, adopting the IPCC RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios (Hausfather et al. 2020). An intermediate dynamical downscaling has been conducted through the configuration of regional climate model COSMO-CLM at ≈ 8 km over Italy, previously provided by Fondazione CMCC (Bucchignani et al. 2016). In Figure 2 it is reported the domain covered by the simulation (within the yellow box) as well as the adopted strategy. The outputs' temporal resolution is hourly and listed in Table 1. Runs cover the whole Italian territory (and neighbouring areas according to the necessary computation boundary, as depicted in Figure 2), therefore it is

a very detailed (in terms of space-time resolution) and comprehensive (in terms of meteorological fields) dataset of projected climatological data for at least 80 years.

Figure 2: Domain of climate projections over Italy

Bioclimatic indicators for wine-growing regions

A selection of key bioclimatic indicators useful to identify the potential of wine-growing regions were identified and assessed in the context of specific case study areas within the framework of project VINO. The case study areas are the Sardinia region and the Oltrepò Pavese. The bioclimatic indicators are listed in Figure 3 with their definition, the used formulae and associated reference, the atmospheric required variables, units and specific notes.

Indicators	Description	Formulae	Reference	Required atmospheric variables	Units	Notes
Cool night Index	Is a thermal index based on the night temperature during the ripening period (Sep. in the N Hemisphere)	$T_{min}(sept)$	Tonietto and Carbonneau, 2004	Daily minimum temperature of <u>September</u>	°C	It improves the assessment of the qualitative potentials of wine-growing regions, notably in relation to secondary metabolites (polyphenols, aromas) in grapes.
Growing Degree Days GDD	The GDD index sums daily effective heat above 10 °C to calculate the amount of heat units incurred over a growing season.	$GDD = \left(\frac{T_{max} + T_{min}}{2} \right) - T_{base}$	McMaster and Wilhelm, 1997	Daily maximum and minimum temperatures	°C	The main limitation of the GDD approach is the overestimation of high temperatures: a very hot summer day will show a high mean daily temperature. This translates into high GDD, meaning optimal conditions for plant growth.
Huglin Index	Thermal index based on degree-days, i.e. on the concept of heat accumulation. Each grape variety requires a certain amount of heat accumulation for optimal ripening to occur	$HI = \sum_{01.04}^{30.09} \left[\frac{(T - 10) + (T_x - 10)}{2} \right] d$	<u>Huglin, 1978</u>	T media e Tmax (Apr-Sept), d length of day coefficient	°C	It represents a similar heat summation formulation to the GDD with an adjustment that gives more weight to maximum temperatures and is multiplied by a coefficient of correction (d) which consider the average daylight period for the latitude studied. It also provides a better idea of the sugar potential according to varieties than the classic temperature sums and, thus, provides qualitative information.
Winkler Index	Sum of GDDs with a base temperature of 10°C. It provides information on the accumulation of heat during the growing season.	$IndWinkler = \sum_{1 April}^{31 October} ((T_{max} + T_{min})/2) - 10$	Amerine and Winkler 1944	Daily minimum and maximum temperature from <u>April to October</u>	°C	
Frost Free Days (FFD)	The <u>frost free</u> days index (FFD) is used to determine growing season length; it is the period between the last frost (temperatures below 0°C) in spring and the first frost in fall.	<u>Number of frost-free days</u>	<u>Magarey et al. 1998</u>	Daily minimum temperature	<u>Number of days</u>	
Dryness index	Assesses soil water availability by providing information on water stress conditions.	$\sum_{April}^{Sept.} (Wo + P - Tv - Es)$	<u>Riou et al., 1994,</u> <u>Tonietto and Carbonneau, 2004</u>	<p>Wo ≡ Initial available soil water reserve (mm)</p> <p>Tv ≡ Potential transpiration in the vineyard (mm) = ETP * k;</p> <p>Jpm = P/5 k(month)</p> <p>Es = direct evaporation from the soil</p>		That climatic factor is important as regards the level of grape ripening and wine quality
Hydrotermic Index	It combines the effect of air humidity (through precipitation) and temperature during the growing season. It allows to study the influence of temperature and precipitation on the grape yield and wine quality and to assess the risk of grape exposure to certain diseases such as mildew.	$\sum_{April}^{Aug} (\bar{T} * P)$	Branas et al., 1946;	Daily rainfall and temperature	mm/°C	

<p>Growing Season Precipitation Index (GSP)</p>	<p>It provides the general suitability used in climate zoning for viticulture that accumulates precipitation during the growing season.</p>	$\sum_{01.04}^{31.09} P$	<p>Blanco-Ward et al., 2007</p>	<p><u>Daily precipitation</u></p>	<p>mm Precipitation during this period can impact the phenology and the berry maturation, and so quality of grapes and grapevine health (disease incidence/severity).</p>
<p>NHH normal heat hour</p>	<p>It allows weighting hourly temperature data based on the four parameters: low cardinal (LC), low optimal cardinal (LOC), upper optimal cardinal (UOC), and upper cardinal (UC).</p>	$NHH = \frac{(2 \cdot (T_d - T_b)^0 + (T_o - T_b)^0 - (T_d - T_b)^{30})}{(T_o - T_b)^{30}}$	<p>Mariani et al., 2012</p>	<p><u>Hourly temperature</u></p>	<p>In detail, hourly temperature gives 0 NHH if outside the cardinal range and 1 NHH if into the optimal range. As temperature moves from LC to LOC, the NHH value linearly increases from 0 to 1.</p>
<p>Biological Effective Degree-Days BEDD</p>	<p>It was developed after observing that plant growth and phenological development respond to temperature in a nonlinear way and finding potential limitations to the standard WI and HI approaches.</p>		<p>Gladstones, 1992</p>	<p><u>Daily temperature</u></p>	<p>The BEDD has three adjustments: (1) the interval of effective heat summation is considered between 10°C (base temperature) and 19°C (upper threshold); (2) a latitude adjustment to account for an increasing day length effect (the same as HI); and (3) a diurnal temperature range adjustment (DTRadj, upward if the DTR is >13°C and downward if <10°C)</p>

Figure 3: Bioclimatic indicators with their definition, formulae, reference, the atmospheric required variables, units and specific notes.

Methodology

The bioclimatic indicators are assessed by considering:

- the current climate mean over the period 1981-2010 of the of specific atmospheric variables derived by VHR-REA_IT dataset is used in the formulae to assess the bioclimatic indicators reported in Figure 3;
- The future climate conditions are calculated in terms of anomalies of specific atmospheric variables derived by the VHR-PRO_IT dataset and used in the formulae to assess the bioclimatic indicators reported in Figure 3. This approach allows assessing the potential changes expected for the future thirty-year period 2021-2050 (centered around the year 2035) and for the future thirty-year period 2036-2065 (centered around the year 2050) compared to the past thirty-year period 1981-2010, considering the IPCC scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 (Hausfather et al. 2020).

Bioclimatic indicators assessment over Sardinia region and Oltrepò Pavese area under current climate (1981-2010)

In Figure 4 the indicators Cool Night index (CNI), Growing Degree Days (GDD10), Winkler index (WI), Huglin index (HI), Frost free days (FFD), Hydrotermic Index (IB), Growing Season Precipitation Index (GSP) and Biological Effective Degree-Days (BBED) are depicted over the Sardinia region assessed over the period 1981-2010 using 2,2 km spatial resolution derived by VHR-REA_IT simulation. The indicator Dryness index is computed following Rio (1994) Tonietto and Carbonneau (2004), using the initial soil water availability as a constant to 200mm as the evapotranspiration was computed using the Thornthwaite (1948) method. The NHH normal heat hour indicator must be clarified with the other collaborators on project VINO for the meaning of the four parameters: low cardinal (LC), low optimal cardinal (LOC), upper optimal cardinal (UOC), and upper cardinal (UC).

Frost free days (FFD)

Hydrotermic Index (IB)

Growing Season Precipitation Index (GSP)

Biological Effective Degree-Days (BBED)

Dryness Index (DI)

Figure 4: Bioclimatic indicators over the Sardinia region assessed over the period 1981-2010 using 2,2km spatial resolution derived by VHR-REA_IT simulation.

In Figure 5 the indicators Cool Night index (CNI), Growing Degree Days (GDD10), Winkler index (WI), Huglin index (HI), Frost free days (FFD), Hydrotermic Index (IB), Growing Season Precipitation Index (GSP) and Biological Effective Degree-Days (BBED) are depicted over the Oltrepò Pavese area assessed over the period 1981-2010 using 2,2km spatial resolution derived by VHR-REA_IT simulation.

Figure 5: Bioclimatic indicators over the Oltrepò Pavese area assessed over the period 1981-2010 using 2,2km spatial resolution derived by VHR-REA_IT simulation.

Bioclimatic indicators anomalies over Sardinia region and Oltrepò Pavese area under climate scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 (periods 2021-2050 and 2036-2065)

In Figure 6 the anomalies of the bioclimatic indicators Cool Night index (CNI), Growing Degree Days (GDD10), Winkler index (WI), Huglin index (HI), Frost free days (FFD), Hydrotermic Index (IB), Growing Season Precipitation Index (GSP) and Biological Effective Degree-Days (BBED) are depicted over the Sardinia region assessed over the period 2021-2050 minus 1981-2010 and 2036-2065 minus 1981-2010 using 2,2km spatial resolution derived by VHR-PRO_IT simulation under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.

Figure 6: Bioclimatic indicators anomalies over the Sardinia region assessed over the periods 2021-2050 and 2036-2065 (reference period 1981-2010) using 2,2km spatial resolution derived by VHR-PRO_IT simulation.

In Figure 7 the anomalies of the bioclimatic indicators Cool Night index (CNI), Growing Degree Days (GDD10), Winkler index (WI), Huglin index (HI), Frost free days (FFD), Hydrotermic Index (IB), Growing Season Precipitation Index (GSP) and Biological Effective Degree-Days (BBED) are depicted over the Oltrepò Pavese area assessed over the period 2021-2050 minus 1981-2010 and 2036-2065 minus 1981-2010 using 2,2km spatial resolution derived by VHR-PRO_IT simulation under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.

Cool Night index (CNI)			
RCP4.5		RCP8.5	
2021-2050	2036-2065	2021-2050	2036-2065

Figure 7: Bioclimatic indicators anomalies over the Oltrepò Pavese area assessed over the periods 2021-2050 and 2036-2065 (reference period 1981-2010) using 2,2km spatial resolution derived by VHR-PRO_IT simulation.

The source files of bioclimatic indicators are delivered in the Milestone M8.3 “Release of climate maps for actual and future projections” in which the data are available as images, raster and shapefiles formats.

References

- Adinolfi, M., Raffa, M., Reder, A. et al. Investigation on potential and limitations of ERA5 Reanalysis downscaled on Italy by a convection-permitting model. *Clim Dyn* 61, 4319–4342 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-023-06803-w>
- Bucchignani, E., Montesarchio, M., Zollo, A.L., Mercogliano, P. (2016). High-resolution climate simulations with COSMO-CLM over Italy: performance evaluation and climate projections for the 21st century. *Int J Climatol* 36(2), 735–756. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.4379>.
- Giorgi, F. (1990). Simulation of regional climate using a limited area model nested in a general circulation model. *Journal of climate*, 3(9), 941-963.
- Hausfather, Z., Peters, G.P. (2020). Emissions – the ‘business as usual’ story is misleading. *Nature* 577, 618–620. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00177-3>.
- Hersbach, H. et al. (2020). The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* 146, 1999–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>.
- Prein, A. F., Langhans, W., Fosser, G., Ferrone, A., Ban, N., Goergen, K., ... & Leung, R. (2015). A review on regional convection-permitting climate modeling: Demonstrations, prospects, and challenges. *Reviews of geophysics*, 53(2), 323-361.
- Raffa, M., Reder, A., Marras, G. F., Mancini, M., Scipione, G., Santini, M., Mercogliano, P. (2021). VHR-REA_IT Dataset: Very High-Resolution Dynamical Downscaling of ERA5 Reanalysis over Italy by COSMO-CLM. *Data* 6(8), 88. <https://doi.org/10.3390/data6080088>.
- Raffa, M., Adinolfi, M., Reder, A. et al. Very High Resolution Projections over Italy under different CMIP5 IPCC scenarios. *Sci Data* 10, 238 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02144-9>
- Rockel, B., Will, A., Hense, A. (2008). The regional climate model COSMO-CLM (CCLM). *Meteorol. Z.* 17, 347–348. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2008/0309>.
- Scoccimarro, E. et al. Effects of tropical cyclones on ocean heat transport in a high resolution coupled general circulation model. *J. Clim.* 24, 4368–4384 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1175/2011JCLI4104.1>
- Tonietto, J., & Carbonneau, A. (2004). A multicriteria climatic classification system for grape-growing regions worldwide. *Agricultural and forest meteorology*, 124(1-2), 81-97.
- McMaster, G. S., & Wilhelm, W. W. (1997). Growing degree-days: one equation, two interpretations. *Agricultural and forest meteorology*, 87(4), 291-300.
- Huglin, M. P. (1978). Nouveau mode d'évaluation des possibilités heliothermiques d'un milieu viticole [climatologie]. *Comptes rendus des Séances de l'Académie d'Agriculture de France*, 64.
- Amerine, M. A., & Winkler, A. J. (1944). Composition and quality of musts and wines of California grapes.
- Branas, J., Bernon, G., & Levadoux, L. (1946). A treatise on the elements of viticulture.
- Blanco-Ward, D., Queijeiro, J. G., & Jones, G. V. (2007). Spatial climate variability and viticulture in the Miño River Valley of Spain. *VITIS-GEILWEILERHOF-*, 46(2), 63.
- Thornthwaite, C. W., & Mather, J. R. (1951). The role of evapotranspiration in climate. *Archiv für Meteorologie, Geophysik und Bioklimatologie, Serie B*, 3, 16-39.